

Improving Vocabulary Through Speech Exercises

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Abstract: The development of speech communication of primary school learners can be achieved by increasing vocabulary, correct use of lexical units, and understanding the differences between oral and written speech. This article discusses issues of expanding learners' vocabulary and the ability to use it in their speech.

Keywords: word, vocabulary, sentence formation, speech, lexical competence, speech communication, speech exercises.

In native language and reading classes in elementary grades, a special place is occupied by the formation of phrases and sentences, retelling the content of the text, telling a story on the topic, creating a text, writing a statement and essay, oral exercises to increase the vocabulary of students to teach them to use vocabulary at the level of automatism, that is, at the level of lexical competence and, finally, at the level of competence.

The methodologist E. I. Passov gives the following explanation of lexical competence: “Lexical competence is a synthesized action of selecting a lexical unit in accordance with the intended idea and correctly combining it with other words, ensuring the situational use of the lexical unit in speech” [1]

S. S. Kuklina and some other scientists believe that lexical skills can only be developed through speech exercises. “Since they (speech exercises) have a situational and communicative focus, associative and subject lexical units determine the semantic features of the meanings of words (...), the acquisition of mechanisms for their selection from the semantic-semantic field, as well as the search, selection and combination in human speech activity ensures the assimilation of probabilistic descriptions. In this case, the (speech) situation introduces the learned LU (lexical units) into a multidimensional system of relations (...). The leading ones among them are situational semantic connections that ensure the pronunciation of the word and the inclusion of the speech idea” [2].

“Speech exercises are as close as possible to natural communication,” but in them “these Lexical Units are not included in speech exercises sequentially, but are given episodically depending on the speech needs of the speaker” [3]. According to S. S. Kuklina, speech exercises aimed at mastering lexical units are not separated from others, do not have the appearance of a targeted exercise; ... do not require the use of all factors of word use, so that it does not fail to have an inhibitory effect.

In the process of speech communication, two types of situations are observed: firstly, the speaker talks in his speech about things and events that do not require deep observation, and secondly, he thinks in his speech about things that require creative thinking. In the first case, the listener or reader simply receives information, and in the second case, he is in the process of searching for answers to the problematic questions that have arisen. In the second situation, the reader encounters a paradigm of words in a certain semantic field in an associative connection and dependence.

In the text, the speech situation is combined with the communicative intention. The speech situation and the process of creating the text differ in the way they arise and their purpose. This difference manifests itself, first of all, in the direction of thought expressed by the speaker and listener in the form of text, with a specific purpose and speech situation. Specific words are selected taking into account the requirements of coherent speech and the needs of the speech situation and have certain differences from each other in style.

Learners' word selection activities are directly related to stylistic rules. Connected speech serves two important purposes in terms of increasing learners' vocabulary: first, it activates words in learners' vocabulary, and second, it simultaneously improves their word selection skills.

The peculiarities of learners' use of vocabulary depend on:

1. the topic of the speech process;
2. the function of speech, the addressee and the purpose of speech;
3. the combination (valence) and semantic characteristics of the words used;
4. the form of speech.

The choice of the first and second words is related to the content of the target speech; and the third and fourth relate to the purpose of using the language units.

Another qualitative change in the vocabulary of learners is manifested in the natural assimilation (through imitation) of a number of words used in everyday communication and social relations. Differences begin to emerge between the rules of literary language and spoken language, which students learn in their native language and in reading classes, and they begin to abandon elements of dialect.

For speech in general and for speech exercises in particular, the speaker must have an idea, a topic related to the idea, and a speech situation. But in the exercise of creating multiple phrases from one word, they will not be available. Therefore, this type of exercise is conditionally included in the list of speech exercises, since it creates a solid foundation for speech development. To create multiple word combinations using one word, you need to choose a word that is familiar to learners, such as school, house, yard, teacher, and what words can be included. The range of meanings of words such as entrepreneur and creator is unfamiliar to children, so the creation of phrases using them is limited (two or three words).

The formation of a sentence occurs in two situations:

1. one-sentence messages and announcements imply both an opinion and a speech situation;
2. the exercise of forming a sentence occurs in such a way that neither a thought nor a speech situation is foreseen.

According to the description, the exercise of composing a sentence based on theoretical information given to learners in class or on a new word learned corresponds primarily to the second case. The words used by the child are also chosen randomly, there is no goal of increasing vocabulary. Therefore, it is better to use tasks related to the first case in order to focus the exercise on a specific goal.

Text retelling exercises, organized for the purpose of speech development, are among the methods widely used in second language teaching methods. A number of sources, including the dissertation of D.R. Toshkhodjaeva [4], show that the following types of retelling exist: detailed retelling of the content of the text (full, expanded, close to the text), retelling of the main content of the text (retelling of the content of the text briefly or abbreviating the text, retelling of the content of the text in your own words), retelling of the content of the text selectively (retelling of part of the text). These types of exercises, in addition to increasing the students' vocabulary, create the basis for a deep and thorough assimilation of new information presented in educational materials and information about national spirituality. At the same time, as D.R. Toshkhodjaeva scientifically and practically substantiated by her research, only retelling the content of the text in one's own words serves the development of learners' speech in all aspects.

Retelling the content of a text that is lexically and grammatically close to the original version will help to further increase learners' vocabulary. The reason is that children use words, phrases, expressions, and syntactic devices in their retellings. If learners are first given new (unfamiliar) words and regularly do vocabulary work, then the task of communicating the main points of the text and using new words can be successfully solved. But if among the new words there are passive words, children will not use them in further speech.

The lexical and grammatical growth of oral speech, as analyzed by A. D. Najimova, is clearly visible in the success of retelling the content of the text "in one's own words." This ability is measured based on a number of parameters:

- the appropriateness of the changes made to the text (correctness or error);
- the use of new words, word forms, syntactic structures;
- replacing bookish words in the text with colloquial ones;
- what the learner "created" by adding himself;
- what is summarized;
- the speaker's personal attitude to reality in the retelling [5].

Undoubtedly, the use of new words and word forms in the learner's retelling indicates that they have begun to be assimilated into speech.

Narrative writing is a written form of retelling the content of a text. In retelling or narrative writing, content is conveyed through text. Unfamiliar words found in the text are considered words to be mastered. It is not necessary to memorize the text to bring the narrative closer to retelling it in your own words. Next, children will have to make up most of the sentences themselves.

In elementary grades, the presentation, written in the native language, is organized into the following types of work:

- retelling and writing a statement in the form of answers to each sentence of the text;
- a statement made after retelling the text at the level of memorization;
- the statement is written after the text has been read a couple of times, after a couple of children have spoken it" [6].

Of course, the first form of writing the statement is less effective. It looks like a typical copywriting exercise.

Narrative exercises on the topic effectively serve to activate the words learned by learners and bring them to the level of automaticity. Learners pay attention to the communicative side of speech in addition to pronouncing words that are characteristic of the style of speech in accordance with the norms of spelling. True, colloquial speech cannot be rich: it uses only actively learned words.

Expression of the development of coherent speech - writing an essay is used as a synonym for expressing the composition (creation) of a text in a later period. Sometimes the latter almost completely replaces the former.

In the elementary grades, exercises that require the creation of text (writing essays) are carried out, although in small quantities. During this type of exercise, students gain some knowledge [7] related to text composition. Not repeating a word in a sentence is one of the hardest skills to learn. If a text describes a person's actions in a row, who represents the person mentioned in the first sentence? If students know that the word that answers the question can be omitted in the next two or three sentences, they will begin to act on this knowledge. For example, a 3rd grade learner wrote the following sentences: Nazira entered the house. She opened his bag. She took out a math textbook.

The learner was not mistaken in repeating the word “Nazira” in every sentence. The size of the text composed in elementary grades ranges from three sentences to 5-6 sentences. The process of writing a text is complicated by the choice of words. A person who writes often forgets what he wants to talk about and thinks only about the sentence he is writing and the word he wants to use in that sentence. Often the right word does not come to mind as quickly as during a conversation; it takes more time to remember and choose it. This process will be accelerated if you complete your writing exercises on time. A learner who begins to become familiar with the rules of text composition also begins to use text synonyms. Some text synonyms are typical for bookish (scientific) speech. Thus, oral and written speech exercises play a major role in increasing learners’ vocabulary.

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